

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: THAPA****FIRST NAME: RAJAN****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 1%

The author used the following software: Microsoft Office on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Why should we mention the source of where the information written about came from?

- Plagiarism is wrong and unethical.
- It is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit.
- It is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences.
- All of the above¹**

2. Which of the following is not included as a basic aspect of English Style Writing?

- Preferred sentence length.
- Readership consideration.
- Use of heading and list.

¹ [Laurent Cleenewerck](#) and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

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Authorization of document.²

3. Which of the following citations is in the correct format?

- According to one scholar, “The railroads had made Chicago the most important meeting place between East and West” (Cronon 1991, 92–93).**³
- According to one scholar (Cronon 1991, 92–93), “The railroads had made Chicago the most important meeting place between East and West”.
- One scholar said, “The railroads had made Chicago the most important meeting place between East and West.”
- None of the above.

4. What are the basic considerations to identify the research aim?

- Research topic.
- Research question.
- Significance.
- All of the above**⁴

5. What are the most common citation forms used in The Turabian rule of style?

Notes-bibliography style, and author-date style⁵

² [Ibid.](#), 41–42.

³ [Kate L.](#) Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: The University of Chicago, 2018), 228.

⁴ [Ibid.](#), 20–21.

⁵ [Ibid.](#), 141.

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- Endnote
 - Footnote and bibliography
 - Quotes citation
6. What are the basic steps to take note systematically in research studies?
- Taking notes on paper.
 - Taking notes electronically and guarding against inadvertent plagiarism.
 - Decide whether to summarize, paraphrase, or quote.
 - All of the above**⁶
7. Which of the following statements is correct?
- The dissertation is the final presentation of the design, execution, and interpretation of the research that was planned in the dissertation prospectus.**⁷
 - The dissertation is referred to as a pre-prospectus paper.
 - The dissertation is a presentation of a literature review.
 - None of the above
8. What are the contributing factors for successful dissertation research?
- Good communication and planning.
 - Using an effective process for writing.

⁶ [Ibid.](#), 48-51.

⁷ [James P. Sampson](#), *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 4.

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Attention to detail and openness to serendipity.

All of the above⁸

9. It is essential to provide evidence that the researcher is reasonably aware that potential positive or negative bias toward various groups of individuals may inappropriately influence the findings.

Because it ensures the data validity.

Because it provides the data transparency.⁹

Because it clarifies the research question.

Because it helps to identify the research hypothesis.

10. Situation requiring citations.

When you quote exact words from the source.

When you paraphrase ideas that are associated with a specific source, even if you don't quote exact words from it.

When you use any ideas, data, or methods attributable to any source you consulted.

All of the above¹⁰

⁸ [Ibid.](#), 13-15.

⁹ [Ibid.](#), 41-42.

¹⁰ [Kate L. Turabian et al.](#), 140.

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